

Identification of varieties and testing of hybrid purity of rice by ultrathin-layer isoelectric focusing of seed protein

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Variety characterization and purity are among the most important requirements of a rice seed lot for sale. Therefore, variety identification, especially through examination of seeds, becomes increasingly important in terms of seed quality control and protection of breeders' rights.

Ultrathin-layer isoelectric focusing (UTLIEF) of seed protein is considered a convenient, quick, cheap, and reliable laboratory method and has been included in the International Seed Testing Association rules for variety verification (ISTA 1999). The cost per kernel of maize purity testing is US\$0.14, \$0.49, and \$1.87 when analyzed by UTLIEF, simple-sequence repeat (SSR) DNA markers, and isozymes, respectively (LUFA Augustenberg, unpubl. data). So far, UTLIEF has not been used in variety testing

of rice. The objective of this study was to identify 20 rice varieties (Fig. 1) collected by the Seed Testing and Applied Botany, State Institute for Agricultural Testing and Research, Augustenberg, Germany, from different countries by UTLIEF.

UTLIEF gels were prepared on polyester support films as described by Radola (1980). The polymerization solution for 10 gels contained 16 g urea, 1.6 g taurine, 50 mL acrylamide (T = 6.8%, C = 2.5%), 4.4 mL ampholytes (Servalyt) pH 2–9, 40 μ L N N N'N'-tetramethylethylenediamine, and 300 μ L of 20% (w/v) ammonium peroxydisulfate. One hundred twenty microliters of a PO_4 buffer solution (1,000 mL of such solution contained 0.194 g K_2HPO_4 , 0.528 g KH_2PO_4 , 25.0 mL glycerine, 1.0 g dithioerythritol, and 0.38 g ethylenediaminetetracetic acid) was used to extract proteins from

individual seed crushed by Kataskapt III (LUFA Augustenberg). About 20 μ L of the supernatant was pipetted onto the 0.15-mm-thick gels and electrophoresis was carried out on Desaga horizontal electrophoresis units (Desaphor, Heidelberg) connected to a cooling apparatus (Haake R) at a temperature of 10 °C for 70 min. After focusing, gels were fixed in 12% (w/v) trichloroacetic acid and stained in Coomassie brilliant blue solution.

Based on the morphological seed characters of the 20 varieties, Egyptian Jasmin (basic seed) and Giza 181 (basic seed) from Egypt; Jinhuzhan, Luhuangzhan, Yuexiangzhan, and Peiza 67 from China; and RD6 (glutinous) and KDML 105 (nonglutinous) from Thailand were classified as indica type with long seed. The remaining 12 varieties were

Fig. 1. Electrophoregram of seed proteins extracted by PO_4 buffer from 20 rice varieties on the gel with Servalyt pH 2–9. M = standard protein markers (isoelectric focusing calibration kit, range pH 3–10, Pharmacia). The pIs of the marker protein bands, from bottom to top, are 8.65, 8.45, 8.15, 7.35, 6.55, 5.85, 5.20, 4.55, and 3.50. Numbers 1 to 12 are Egyptian Jasmin (basic seed), Giza 178 (basic seed), Giza 178 (Gharbia), Giza 171 (Gharbia), Giza 176 (basic seed), Giza 177 (basic seed), Giza 177 (Gharbia), Giza 181 (basic seed), Sakha 101 (basic seed), Sakha 101 (Gharbia), Sakha 102 (basic seed), and Sakha 102 (Gharbia) from Egypt; 13 to 16 are Jinhuzhan, Luhuangzhan, Yuexiangzhan, and Peiza 67 from China; 17 and 18 are A and B varieties from the Philippines; 19 and 20 are RD6 (glutinous) and KDML 105 (nonglutinous) from Thailand. ○ = indica.

classified as japonica type with short seed. In the electrophoregram (Fig.1), 34–40 protein bands were identified for each variety. Among the many protein bands, 10 distinct bands were polymorphic among the 20 varieties tested, with pI (isoelectric point) values of 4.40, 5.06, 6.01, 6.38, 6.49, 6.75, 7.00, 7.24, 7.58, and 8.38. With these polymorphic protein bands and morphological characters of seeds, eight indica and three japonica [Giza 178 (basic seed), Giza 178 (Gharbia), and variety A from the Philippines] varieties could be distinguished from each other. The other nine japonica varieties could be in two subgroups; the electrophoregram was similar in each subgroup. Other protocols of the UTLIEF such as different protein extraction solutions, ampholytes of different pH ranges, different focusing distances between anode and cathode, and other staining methods (silver staining) could be used to further discriminate the varieties in the two japonica subgroups. This result shows that UTLIEF can be used to discriminate among rice varieties, even among genetically close varieties such as Giza 178 (basic seed), Giza 178 (Gharbia), and Giza 181 (basic seed).

A two-line breeding technique using photothermosensitive genic male sterile (PTGMS) indica rice (Peiai 64S) as the male sterile line and maintainer line is being developed in China and some other countries. However, the purity of the F₁ seeds of two-line hybrid rice is usually low because the PTGMS line will self-pollinate when light and temperature conditions are not met. Therefore, testing the hybrid purity of F₁ seeds of two-line hybrid rice is

becoming increasingly important. Figure 2 shows the electrophoregram of seed proteins from a two-line hybrid combination: Peiai 64S/P119. One protein marker band (D) was found to exist in the PTGMS line Peiai 64S in the pH range used, whereas the restorer line P119 had three marker bands (A, B, and C). Therefore, the real hybrid F₁ seeds of Peiai 64S/P119 should contain bands A, B, and C from the restorer line and band D from the male sterile line. Figure 2 shows that, of the four individual F₁ seeds tested, one seed had only the marker band from Peiai 64S. This F₁ seed was inbred. The other three F₁

seeds had four marker bands (A, B, C, and D) from both P119 and Peiai 64S, and thus were considered real hybrids.

A field test is being carried out to confirm the UTLIEF results.

References

- ISTA (International Seed Testing Association). 1999. International rules for seed testing. Annexes 1999. Seed Sci. Technol. 27 (supplement).
- Radola BJ. 1980. Ultrathin-layer isoelectric focusing in 50–100 mm polyacrylamide gels on silanized glass plate or polyester films. *Electrophoresis* 1:43–56.

Fig. 2. Electrophoregram of proteins extracted by 30% 2-chloroethanol of parent and F₁ seeds of two-line hybrid combination (Peiai 64S/P119) rice on the gel with Servalyt pH 4–9.

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